

Development and Evaluation of Functional Muffins Enriched with Pomegranate Peel Powder: A Sustainable Approach to Food Waste Valorization

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Abstract

Pomegranate peel, a major by-product of pomegranate processing, is rich in dietary fiber, minerals, and bioactive compounds, making it a promising ingredient for the development of value-added food products. The present study aimed to develop nutritionally enriched muffins by incorporating pomegranate peel powder at different levels and to evaluate their sensory acceptability. Pomegranate peels were dried, powdered, and analyzed for their proximate and mineral composition. Muffins were prepared by partially replacing whole wheat flour with pomegranate peel powder at levels of 3 g, 6 g, and 8 g, while a control sample without pomegranate peel powder was also developed. Nutritional analysis revealed that pomegranate peel powder contained appreciable amounts of crude fiber (17.30 g/100 g), calcium (330.56 mg/100 g), iron (6.28 mg/100 g), and potassium (144.60 mg/100 g). Sensory evaluation was conducted using a nine-point hedonic scale by a semi-trained panel. Among all formulations, muffins containing 6 g pomegranate peel powder achieved the highest overall acceptability score (8.61), followed by 3 g pomegranate peel powder, control, and 8 g pomegranate peel powder samples. The findings suggest that pomegranate peel powder can be successfully incorporated into muffins to enhance their nutritional quality while promoting the sustainable utilization of food processing by-products.

Keywords: Pomegranate peel powder; Muffins; Food waste utilization; Nutritional enrichment; Functional foods; Sensory evaluation; Bakery product fortification

1. Introduction

Every year, nearly one-third of the food produced globally is either lost or wasted, with this figure increasing to around 40% in developed countries. The FAO Food Loss Index monitors food losses at the national level across the entire supply chain, from agricultural production to retail. According to FAO estimates, this results in a global food loss of about 13.8%. Pomegranate peel (PP) alone is believed to contribute approximately 1.6 billion tons to the world's annual food waste (Singh et al., 2023). Pomegranate (*Punica granatum*), a member of the Punicaceae family, derives its name from the Latin term *malum granatum*, meaning "granular apple." Its peel is the tough, inedible outer layer of the fruit, made up of two distinct parts: the pericarp and the mesocarp (El Barnossi et al., 2021).

Pomegranate production and consumption have been steadily increasing due to its desirable taste and nutritional value. In 2017, global production was estimated at approximately 3.8 million tons. The fruit is composed of three main parts: peel, juice, and seeds. It is commonly consumed fresh or processed into juice, however, juice processing generates a significant amount of waste, with the peel accounting for nearly 26–30% of the total fruit weight (Mo et al., 2022).

The peel is rich in polyphenols, highlighting the pharmacological potential of pomegranate due to their anticancer properties. Studies have also shown that the peel contains a higher

concentration of bioactive compounds compared to other parts of the fruit (Chauhan & Chauhan, 2024). The use of byproducts generated during pomegranate processing, which are rich in valuable bioactive compounds, offers significant potential for developing a variety of products. These include industrial enzymes, functional ingredients that enhance food quality, and additives used in the food industry to improve shelf life (Charalampia & Koutelidakis, 2017).

Cookies are among the most widely consumed bakery snacks. They are popular across age groups due to their affordability, convenience, nutritional value, and long shelf life. Consumed globally, cookies are typically made from refined flour, hydrogenated fat, sugar, emulsifiers, and small amounts of other additives. Their nutritional quality can be enhanced through fortification or by incorporating non-wheat flours (Muhammad et al., 2023). Incorporating PP into muffins can increase their flavonoid and anthocyanin levels, thereby improving their nutritional value as well as their sensory, rheological, and antioxidant properties (Ismail et al., 2014).

In this study, refined wheat flour was fortified with varying levels of pomegranate peel powder to produce muffins with enhanced nutritional and therapeutic value. The addition of peel powder increased the fiber and mineral content, which may help reduce the risk of conditions such as osteoporosis and anaemia. This fortification strategy offers a simple and cost-effective approach to improving health outcomes.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

Pomegranate were purchased from local market of Banasthali Vidyapith, Tonk, Rajasthan. The peels were separated, thoroughly washed, and cut into small pieces (approximately 1 × 1 cm). They were then tray-dried in an oven at 40°C for 5–6 hours. Once dried, the peels were ground into a coarse powder using a blender, sieved through a 250 µm mesh to ensure uniformity, and were stored in air tight containers. Figure 1 illustrates the different forms of pomegranate utilized during the preparation of PPP including (a) pomegranate fruit, (b) fresh peel, (c) dried peel, and (d) pomegranate peel powder (PPP).

Figure 1. Pomegranate forms: (a) fruit, (b) peel, (c) dried peel, and (d) peel powder

2.2 Nutritional assessment

The proximate composition of the powder was evaluated using standard analytical methods. Moisture content was determined by the air oven method, ash by the muffle furnace method, protein by the micro-Kjeldahl method, crude fat using a Soxhlet apparatus, and crude fibre through the acid–alkali digestion method. Carbohydrate content was calculated by difference. All procedures were carried out following established standard methods (Raghuramulu et al.,

1983; AOAC, 1995). Mineral content (calcium, potassium, iron, and zinc) of PPP, fortified wheat flour, and muffins was determined using the method described by Khan et al (2016).

2.3 Standardization and formulation of muffins enriched with PPP

A control sample was prepared by homogeneously mixing 140 g of whole wheat flour, 65 g of sugar, 50 g of butter, 1.5 g of baking powder, and 120 ml of milk to obtain a smooth and pourable batter, without the addition of PPP. For fortification, whole wheat flour was partially replaced with PP powder at varying levels, namely: 137 g flour + 3 g PP powder, 134 g flour + 6 g PP powder, and 132 g flour + 8 g PP powder. The quantities of sugar, butter, baking powder, and milk were kept constant across all treatments. All ingredients were thoroughly mixed to obtain a uniform batter, which was then poured into muffin moulds of equal size. The samples were baked at 180°C for 18–20 minutes. After baking, the muffins were cooled to room temperature and stored in airtight containers for further analysis. Each treatment was conducted in triplicate. The formulation of muffins enriched with different levels of pomegranate peel powder is presented in Table 1. The control sample was prepared without pomegranate peel powder, while the experimental formulations were developed by partially replacing whole wheat flour with varying amounts of PPP as 3 g for B, 6 g for C and 8 g for D.

Table 1. Formulation of muffins enriched with PPP

Ingredients	Control (A)	3 g (B)	6 g (C)	8 g (D)
Whole wheat flour (g)	140	137	134	132
Pomegranate peel powder (g)	0	3	6	8
Sugar (g)	65	65	65	65
Butter (g)	50	50	50	50
Baking powder (g)	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Milk (ml)	120	120	120	120

2.4 Sensory Evaluation

The sensory attributes of muffins were evaluated by a panel of twelve semi-trained members from the department of Food Science and Nutrition, Banasthali Vidyapith. The panelists were instructed to assess the samples based on parameters such as appearance, colour, flavour and taste, texture, aftertaste/mouthfeel, and overall acceptability. The evaluation of different muffin variants was carried out using a nine-point hedonic scale along with the score card method (Pinki & Awasthi, 2012).

3. Results and Discussion

The proximate composition of the developed food product enriched with PPP was evaluated. The moisture content was found to be 7.19 g, ash 4.30 g, fat 0.53 g, protein 3.60 g, crude fiber 17.30 g, and nitrogen-free extract (NFE) 64.81 g. The mineral composition revealed calcium content of 330.56 mg, potassium 144.60 mg, iron 6.28 mg, and zinc 1.08 mg, as presented in Table 2. The proximate composition obtained in the present study was found to be comparable with earlier findings. Ranjitha et al. (2018) reported moisture 7.27 g, ash 4.32 g, fat 0.85 g, protein 3.74 g, crude fiber 17.31 g, and nitrogen-free extract 66.51 g. Similarly, Srivastava et al. (2014) observed moisture 6.02 g, ash 4.23 g, fat 0.41 g, protein 3.38 g, and crude fiber 31.10

g. Abbas et al. (2025) also reported moisture 4.6 g, ash 5.31 g, fat 2.4 g, protein 6.73 g, crude fiber 21 g, and nitrogen-free extract 53.26 g in PPP. Table 2 depicts the nutritional composition of PPP.

Table 2. Nutritional composition of PPP

Nutrient	Value per 100 g
Moisture	7.19 g
Ash	4.30 g
Fat	0.53 g
Protein	3.60 g
Fiber	17.30 g
NFE	64.81 g
Calcium	330.56 mg
Potassium	144.60 mg
Iron	6.28 mg
Zinc	1.08 mg

3.2. Standardization and Development of PPP Enriched Muffins

Based on the formulation described above, three variants of muffins enriched with PPP along with a control sample were prepared. The developed muffin formulations containing different levels of pomegranate peel powder are presented in Figure 2. The formulations included a control sample and muffins fortified with 3 g, 6 g, and 8 g of pomegranate peel powder.

Figure 2. Muffin formulations prepared with different levels of pomegranate peel powder: Control (A), 3 g PPP (B), 6 g PPP (C), and 8 g PPP (D)

3.3. Sensory Evaluation

The acceptability of muffins was evaluated by a panel of twelve members. The sensory evaluation using a 9-point hedonic scale indicated that the most acceptable variant was sample C containing 6 g of PPP, followed by sample B with 3 g, sample A (control) without PPP, and sample D with 8 g of PPP. The sensory evaluation scores of control and PPP - enriched muffins are presented in Table 3. The muffins were assessed for colour, taste, texture, appearance, aftertaste, and overall acceptability using a nine-point hedonic scale by a semi-trained sensory panel.

Table 3. Sensory mean scores of muffins fortified with PPP determined using a nine-point hedonic scale

Sensory attributes	Muffin	PPP enriched cookies		
	A Control recipe	B (3 g)	C (6 g)	D (8 g)
Colour	7.31 ± 0.31	7.45 ± 0.33	7.77 ± 0.45	7.45 ± 0.54
Taste	8.2 ± 0.12	8.44 ± 0.23	8.54 ± 0.56	8.37 ± 0.49
Texture	7.91 ± 0.53	7.8 ± 0.56	7.5 ± 0.53	7.3 ± 0.41
Appearance	7.5 ± 0.63	7.3 ± 0.56	7.45 ± 0.45	7.1 ± 0.64
Aftertaste	7.8 ± 0.44	7.98 ± 0.34	7.56 ± 0.62	7.47 ± 0.61
Overall acceptability	7.74 ± 0.40	7.79 ± 0.40	7.76 ± 0.52	7.53 ± 0.53

The mean sensory scores of the control and PPP-fortified muffin variants are presented in Figure 3. The sensory attributes evaluated included colour, taste, texture, appearance, aftertaste, and overall acceptability.

Figure 3. Mean sensory analysis data of various muffins variants fortified with PPP

4. Conclusion

The findings of the present study indicate that PPP is a valuable source of several nutrients. It contains appreciable amounts of crude fiber and moisture along with a moderate quantity of protein. In addition, it is rich in minerals such as iron and calcium, which enhances its nutritional significance. These characteristics make PPP a suitable ingredient for incorporation into various food products. In the present study, PP powder was utilized for the enrichment of cookies, and among all the variants, sample C was found to be the most acceptable, followed by samples B, A, and D.

The results of the present study emphasize the potential of PPP as a beneficial ingredient in the development of value-added food products, thereby creating opportunities for further research and application. Future studies may focus on optimizing the incorporation of PPP into a broader range of bakery and functional food products to improve their nutritional quality and sensory characteristics. In addition, further research may evaluate the stability of bioactive compounds present in PP, including antioxidants and polyphenols, under different processing and storage

conditions to ensure maximum retention of their health-promoting properties. Another important area of investigation could involve the formulation of specialized food products such as high-fiber and low-fat foods intended to support overall health and wellness.

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